

Young Researchers in Archaeometry

YRA Workshop 2025

October 14–17, 2025

Budapest, Hungary

Abstract Book

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**SUBCOMMITTEE ON ARCHAEOOMETRY,
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Programme

Tuesday, 14 October

19:00 Icebreaker (self-paid)
Treffort Kert és Könyvtár Klub (1088 Budapest, Múzeum krt. 4.)

Wednesday, 15 October

09:00 – 09:30 Registration

09:30 – 09:50 Welcome

09:50 – 10:20 Keynote: Communities, connectivity and catastrophes in 6th century Pannonia: Challenges and possibilities of combining genetic, archaeological and historical perspectives
István Koncz
Session 1: Pigments, plaster and mortars

10:20 – 10:40 The inter-instrumental comparability of semi-quantitative ED-XRF analyses of iron gall inks
Ophelia Kloth

10:40 – 11:00 Painters by the Yarmouk: Investigating Craft Organisation through Painted Plaster Analysis at Gadara and Tall Zira'a (Northern Jordan)
Elena Cantero Ros, Luc Megens, Brita Jansen, Hans Huisman, Susanne Kerner

11:00 – 11:20 Distinguishing binder to aggregate ratio in historic lime mortars from Cyprus through FTIR analysis: is it really possible?
Paola Pizzo, Petra Mácová, Jan Válek

11:20 – 11:40 *Coffee break*

11:40 – 12:00 *Awards ceremony*

Session 2: Glass and building materials

12:00 – 12:20 Beyond Provenance: Reconstructing Exchange Routes, Production Processes, and Recycling based on Early Medieval Glass Beads from Zweeloo (the Netherlands)
Nina Schreuder

- 12:20 – 12:40 Research on Burnt Early Copper Age Houses at Marosnagylak
Eszter Horváth, Dorottya Láng, András Füzesi
- 12:40 – 13:00 A close-up on prehistorical household structures. Case study:
micromorphology in the Bronze Age tell settlement from Sântion - Movila
Mănăstirii (Bihor county, Romania)
Alexandra Stache, Florin Gogâltan, Emanoil Săsăran
- 13:00 – 14:00 *Lunch break*
- Session 3: Metals*
- 14:00 – 14:20 Comparison of the polychrome metalworking and decorative techniques
from the Langobardic and Gepidic periods (late 5th and 6th centuries AD) in
the Carpathian Basin
Viktória Mozgai, Eszter Horváth, László Előd Aradi, Bernadett Bajnóczi
- 14:20 – 14:40 Identifying surface treatments on medieval metal artefacts
András Török
- 14:40 – 15:00 The datability of Nuremberger yellow brass
Panni Kovács
- 15:00 – 15:20 The TerraLID metadata profile: Uniformly describing lead isotope data in
archaeology
*Thomas Rose, Tim Greifelt, Katrin J. Westner, Annette Hornschuch, Yiu-Kang
Hsu, Helge Wiethoff, Sabine Klein*
- 15:20 – 15:40 *Coffee break*
- 16:00 – 18:00 Guided tour in the Hungarian National Museum (1088 Budapest, Múzeum
krt. 14–16.)

Thursday, 16 October

- 09:00 – 11:30 Visit at the Budapest Neutron Centre (1121 Budapest, Konkoly-Thege
Miklós út 29–33.) or ELTE RCH Institute of Archaeogenomics (1097
Budapest, Tóth Kálmán utca 4.)
- 11:30 – 13:20 *Lunch break*

Bioarchaeology, part 1

- 13:20 – 13:40 Strontium Isotopic and Proteomic Analyses on the Human Remains of the KGK VI sites of Sultana and Gumelnița, Romania
Aurelien Tafani, Enrico Greco, Robert H. Tykot, Kévin Salesse, Hannah F. James, Christophe Snoeck, Cătălin Lazăr
- 13:40 – 14:00 Early Thoughts on Childhood in Early Medieval Iceland (10th–13th Centuries AD)
Maren von Mallinckrodt
- 14:00 – 14:20 Gender, Age, and Social Identity in the Middle Bronze Age Burials from Western Hungary
Eszter Melis Tamás Hajdu, Anett Gémes, Katalin Gyenesei, Fabian Kanz, István Major, Attila Mrenka, Katharina Rebay-Salisbury, Bálint Savanyú, Viktória Kiss
- 14:20 – 14:40 *Coffee break*
- 14:40 – 16:00 Poster Session (see tab “Posters”)
- Session 5: Bioarchaeology, part 2*
- 16:00 – 16:20 The Whole, the Missing and the Disturbed- Exploring Post-Burial Practices in the Langobard Cemetery of Gyirmót–Homokdomb
Regina Viktória Csordás, Eliza Orellana-González
- 16:20 – 16:40 Experimental research of medieval bone skates
Kata Szathmári
- 16:40 – 17:00 Archaeozoological investigations in the Late Neolithic site of Moftinu Mare-Hamiliz (Northwest Romania)
Xenia Pop
- 17:00 – 17:20 Ancient Parasitic Infection: A Millennium-Old Probable Echinococcal Cyst Discovered in an Avar Period Burial
Csilla Libor, László Előd Aradi, Norbert Kapcsos M., Kristóf Fehér, Botond Heltai, Dániel Gerber, Tamás Sréter, Dániel Csete, Gergely Szenthe, Erwin Gáll
- 20:30 Conference dinner (self-paid)
Vakvarjú Étterem Pest (1061 Budapest Paulay Ede u. 7.)

Friday, 17 October

Session 6: Ceramics, part 1

- 09:00 – 09:20 Pottery Technology and Neolithization in the Middle Tagus Basin: Preliminary Petrographic Insights
Estíbaliz Espada-Martín, Miriam Cubas, Silvia Amicone
- 09:20 – 09:40 Understanding Copper Age pottery function through morphometric and organic residue analysis
Rebeka Solti, Isabel Wiltshire, Izzy Davis, Melanie Roffet-Salque, Lucy Cramp, Eszter Solnay, Márton Szilágyi, Dávis Kraus, Gábor Szilas, Zsuzsanna M. Virág, Zsuzsanna Siklósi
- 09:40 – 10:00 The traces of the potter's hand: Pottery experimental reference collection for the analysis of Copper Age vessels from the Carpathian Basin
Eszter Solnay, Zita Hrabák, Antony Borel
- 10:00 – 10:20 Technological investigation of the Middle Bronze Age Late Hatvan and Füzesabony style pottery from the Borsod plain region, Northeastern Hungary
Ákos Mengyán, Klára P. Fischl, Ferenc Kristály
- 10:20 – 10:40 Comparing archaic Corinthian pottery through SEM-EDS and optical microscopy. A case study
Michael Ioannou
- 10:40 – 11:00 *Coffee break*

Session 7: Ceramics, part 2

- 11:00 – 11:20 Unchanging tastes: Material choices in Hellenistic and Roman storage vessels from Nea Paphos
Zofia Chomonicik
- 11:20 – 11:40 Geochemical and mineralogical provenance analysis of West African pottery
Juan-Marco Puerta Schardt, Andreas Gaertner
- 11:40 – 12:00 Exploring AI-assisted Image Segmentation for Ceramic Thin Section Analysis: some Experience with TagLab
Elisabetta di Virgilio, Federico Parisi, Diego Ronchi, Antonio Ferrandes, Marco Callieri
- 12:00 – 12:20 Iberian majolica finds in the medieval Kingdom of Hungary?
Dorottya Györkös, Zsófia Náday, László Előd Aradi, Kristóf Fehér, Erika Kereskényi, Attila Kreiter

12:20 – 13:40 *Lunch break*

Session 8: Geoarchaeology and geophysics

13:40 – 14:00 Prehistoric Sites in Turkmenistan: A GIS-Based Overview of Spatial and Temporal Patterns

Mahym Amanova

14:00 – 14:20 Geophysical research of rural settlements of the Roman period in the surroundings of Crumerum (Nyergesújfalu, Hungary)

Viola Tőkés

14:20 – 14:40 Application of Non-Destructive Field Investigation Methods in the Archaeological Study of a Medieval Ruined Settlement in Tolna County, Hungary

Mátyás Németh

14:40 – 15:00 Closing

Posters

Bioarchaeology, diet, mobility

- The Lord of the Shrooms: A Sensor's Quest to Detect Ancient Ergot
Justina Stonyte, Paulina Morkyte, Giedre Motuzaitė Matuzeviciute, Rasa Pauliukaite

Ceramics, pottery, glazes

- Urns Under the Microscope: Petrographic analysis of eight Iron Age pots from Funen, Denmark
Christina Holdgaard Schultze, Torbjörn Brorsson
- Archaeometric analysis of late Sarmatian pottery recovered from Tázlár-Templomhegy settlement
Vivien Bozsik, Krisztián Fintor, Sándor Gulyás, Dorottya Walter, Dorottya Györkös, Attila Kreiter, Máté Szemerédi
- Clay and pots from Eneolithic period
Mădălina Dimache

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- Blue and Pink Across the Strait: Stylistic, Material, and Technical Study of 20th-Century Japanese and Taiwanese Ceramic Tableware
Han-Chun (Joanna) Hsieh
- First Archaeometric Results on Early Iron Age Ceramic Fragments from the Sanctuary of Apollo Pythios in Gortyn, Crete
Bianca Costi Farias, Anna Bertelli, Lara Maritan, Jacopo Bonetto

Pigments, mortars

- Characterization and Analysis of Wall Painting Fragments from the Sandrigo Estate of Aquileia for the Determination of a Chronological Framework
Yarden Jessica Tsoni, Clelia Sbrolli, Andrea Cipolato, Daniela Cottica, Simone Dilaria
- Archaeometric analyses of Pozzolan Mortars in Roman Thermal and Hydraulic Constructions at Nora, Sardinia
Laura Buganza, Zeno Caneva, Jacopo Bonetto, Caterina Previato, Simone Dilaria

Organic materials, organic residues, textiles

- Textile remains of the Early Avar period cemetery at Babarc
Flórián Harangi

Lithics, stones, building materials

- Tracing the Provenance of Roman Marble Statues through Multi-Proxy Analysis
Vasiliki Anevlavi, Kalina Petkova, Vesselka Katsarova, Petya Andreeva, Walter Prochaska

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The Inter-instrumental Comparability of Semi-quantitative ED-XRF Analyses of Iron Gall Inks

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Keywords: Iron gall inks, XRF

A systematic chemical investigation of ancient and medieval inks from known socio-geographic contexts could enable a non-invasive, indirect dating of manuscripts. This prospect led to the development of a standardised protocol for the in-situ analysis of inks in historical manuscripts, incorporating energy dispersive X-ray fluorescence (ED-XRF) spectroscopy. Due to the heterogeneous, thin-layered ink-on-support matrix, ED-XRF analyses of inks are limited to semi-quantitative results. Given the wide variety of configurations in ED-XRF spectrometers, concerns persist regarding the comparability of data generated by different devices. This study addresses these concerns by analysing mock-ups with known ink compositions and a historical manuscript sample using five ED-XRF spectrometers. The results reveal significant discrepancies in relative elemental intensities across spectrometers, linked to factors as the anode material, X-ray optics, incident angle, and acquisition mode. These findings underscore the need for detailed metadata, robust calibration routines, and the use of standard reference materials in the ED-XRF analysis of writing materials. The study calls for greater dialogue among heritage scientists to refine analytical protocols for ink analysis, in order to support reproducible and interoperable data across laboratories and ultimately pave the way for a reliable ink database.

Painters by the Yarmouk: Investigating Craft Organisation through Painted Plaster Analysis at Gadara and Tall Zira'a (Northern Jordan)

Elena Cantero Ros^{1*}, Luc Megens², Susanne Kerner⁵

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Keywords: Multi-method analysis, Wall paintings, Craft networks, Hellenistic-Roman Levant

Excavated between 1992 and 1995, the painted plasters of Area 44 at Gadara (Umm Qais, Jordan) are one of the few Hellenistic and Roman domestic painting assemblages found in the Levant. The paintings received little attention until recent excavations at nearby Tall Zira'a revealed a new corpus of paintings executed identically. Most fragments, corresponding to the so-called "Masonry Style", exhibit an impressed stone decoration in yellow and red with a painting technique previously undocumented. The striking similarity suggests they were the work of the same craftspeople. In this context, the composition of plasters, aggregates and pigments offers invaluable insights into the logistics and production processes of painted decorations made by local workshops. In collaboration with the German Protestant Institute of Archaeology in Amman and the Cultural Heritage Agency of the Netherlands, twenty-three fragments were shipped to Amsterdam for a multi-method analytical study. The techniques included μ XRF, pXRF, XRD, FTIR, SEM-EDS with cross-sections and photo-induced luminescence (VIL, UV, IR). The results revealed the use of several kinds of red ochre and application techniques within the same wall, but not between the stone imitation fragments of both sites. This suggests painters may have worked independently across the same region, with a trusted supply of raw materials, and developed projects in collaboration with other craftspeople.

Distinguishing Binder to Aggregate Ratio in Historic Lime Mortars from Cyprus through FTIR Analysis: Is it Really Possible?

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Keywords: B:A ratio, Calcite, FTIR, Lime binder

This paper offers new perspectives on the use of Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) analysis for the identification of calcite types in lime mortars. Calcite (CaCO_3) is the predominant component of lime binders, which is obtained by burning limestone rocks or other calcareous materials. The resulting pyrogenic product is often mixed with geogenic and biogenic components during the production of the mortar. FTIR has proved to be an effective analytical tool in the distinction between pure geogenic, pure biogenic, and pure pyrogenic calcites; thus, this paper aims at demonstrating the potential of this technique in distinguishing also mixtures' proportions. The methodology is based on previously published studies proving how the shape, height, and area of the main calcite peaks – in particular ν_2 and ν_4 – in FTIR spectra change according to the formation process of the calcitic material. The present paper reveals how the calculation of the ν_2/ν_4 area ratios, can indicate the presence of mixed types of calcites, and aid in estimating the percentages. The results obtained show how – in the presence of a valuable reference database – it is possible to distinguish ranges of limestone:lime mixtures. This methodological study was applied on a set of samples collected in the district of Paphos, in South Western Cyprus. The geogenic and biogenic samples are representative of the main geological formations and faunal species of the region, while the archaeological samples were collected at the site of Nea Paphos. The pyrogenic calcite specimens were produced in controlled laboratory setting.

Beyond Provenance: Reconstructing Exchange Routes, Production Processes, and Recycling based on Early Medieval Glass Beads from Zweeloo (The Netherlands)

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Keywords: Glass, XRF, Chemical composition, Early Medieval period, The Netherlands, Exchange routes

This study investigates approximately 300 glass beads from the early medieval cemetery of Zweeloo (the Netherlands; ca. 400-900 CE) by combining typological and chemical analysis (pXRF). The aim is to reconstruct exchange networks, trace possible material supply routes, and identify recycling processes, thereby gaining a more complete understanding of all stages in the bead-making sequence. Additionally, this study highlights the benefits of a typo-chronological approach in which chemical composition analysis is firmly embedded. The chemical composition of the beads from Zweeloo reveals multiple base glass types, reflecting origins in the Mediterranean and Southeast Asia. The chemical data has varied outcomes, points to groups of beads that were produced together and stayed together until they were deposited in the cemetery, while at the same time indicating the reuse and recycling of glass that took place. Typological and compositional data also reveal that beads from different chronological phases co-occur in individual graves, suggesting prolonged circulation of the objects, possibly as heirlooms. By integrating chemical composition with typological and contextual information, this research explores glass bead production and circulation. It also shows how a typo-chronological approach can help to further define known beadgroups - from raw glass composition to recycling and final deposition. Overall, the beads from Zweeloo demonstrate how archaeometric analysis can illuminate the complexity of early medieval exchange patterns and bead-making traditions across regions.

Research on Burnt Early Copper Age Houses at Marosnagylak

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Keywords: Daub imprint analysis, Copper age house, Daub typology, Cucuteni-Trypillia Culture

In the summer of 2024, the remains of an Early Copper Age house, destroyed by intentional burning, were excavated at Marosnagylak (Romania). Following the fieldwork, two separate one-week sessions were conducted to undertake intensive post-excavation analysis. Although the processing of the material is still ongoing, preliminary observations and the documentation of a significant number of daub fragments have already yielded valuable insights into the structure of the house, the intensity of the fire, and the dynamics of the collapse. Twenty distinct material types were identified, primarily based on temper composition and the degree of thermal alteration. Spatial distribution analysis of these types provided further data on fire intensity and propagation. Imprint analysis revealed several morphological categories (straight, curved, right-angled); within the curved group, subcategories were established based on diameter, suggesting different architectural components (twigs, stakes, posts). The density and typology of impressions allowed for the partial reconstruction of structural units, including flooring, corner elements, and wall fabrics. The most informative fragments were documented through precise measurements, high-resolution photography, and detailed drawings. Ethnographic and archaeological analogies were also considered in interpreting the architectural elements. Combined analysis of material composition, burning intensity, and spatial patterns suggests a structure that collapsed inward. Continued analysis is expected to provide further insights into the building's life cycle and the circumstances surrounding its final destruction.

A Close-up on Prehistorical Household Structures, Case Study: Micromorphology in the Bronze Age Tell Settlement from Sântion-Movila Mănăstirii (Bihar County, Romania)

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Keywords: Micromorphology, Middle Bronze Age, Tell settlement, Households

Tell settlements are artificial mounds formed through successive accumulation of constructions remains. The Sântion - Movila Mănăstirii tell settlement is known archaeologically since 1871. It belongs to the Middle Bronze Age and is overlaid by a medieval monastery and a modern road that crosses the entire site. The ceramic style is characteristic of the Otomani II culture and the absolute data that we have places the habitation of the tell between 1892-1631 BC.

In this study we try to see the microscopical details of the northern profile (3.42 m) of the last excavation in the tell from 2023. On this matter we first collected 12 samples and another batch of 9 samples later. With these samples we cover almost every archaeological context that is present in the northern profile, including construction materials or fillings from different stages of the tell. We collected the samples in aluminium boxes, then we air-dried them for a while. We treated them with polyester resin and put them in vacuum. After each sample was dry, we polished them and then cut them into thin sections.

This research is approaching the site through geological methods. We focus on the sediments and the organic material that is found in the anthropogenic levels. The reason of this approach is observing the dynamic of the households and structures as well as the expendability of a space in the Middle Bronze Age. Through micromorphology we also focus on the evolution of the building technique, whether intentional or accidental.

Comparison of the Polychrome Metalworking and Decorative Techniques from the Langobardic and Gepidic periods (Late 5th and 6th Centuries AD) in the Carpathian Basin

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Keywords: Polychrome metalwork, 6th century AD, Carpathian Basin, Niello, Garnet, SEM-EDX, hXRF, μ -XRD, Raman spectroscopy

The polychrome decoration of fine metalwork objects, particularly the use of red garnet inlays, was widespread during the Hellenistic, Roman and Early Medieval times, representing an intercultural and supra-regional fashion in Europe. In the archaeological material of the Carpathian Basin this polychromy was characteristic over around three centuries, from the Hunnic Period through the age of the Gepidic and Langobardic Kingdoms up until the Avar Period. While 5th century artworks tend to be unique, artefacts from the subsequent decades exhibit closer resemblances to mass-produced items characterised by many common features. During the first two-thirds of the 6th century, the territory of the Carpathian Basin was ruled by two Germanic tribes with different origins and histories: the Gepids settled in the Tisza region and the Langobards in Transdanubia. This study focuses on these two regions, exploring the differences and similarities, as well as the chronological and regional changes in the use of raw materials, metalworking and decoration techniques, and the supply of garnets. Nearly a hundred gold, gilded silver, and copper-based alloy objects from the collections of the Hungarian museums, dated to the late 5th and 6th centuries AD, were analysed in detail by using non-destructive and non-invasive analytical methods (optical microscopy, handheld XRF, SEM-EDX, μ -XRD, Raman spectroscopy) to determine the chemical composition of the metal alloys and their decorations (gilding, niello and garnet), the mineral inclusion characteristics of the garnets, as well as the microstructure and mineralogical composition of the niello.

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Identifying Surface Treatments on Medieval Metal Artefacts

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Keywords: Archaeometallurgy, XRF, Silvering, Tinning

The research of surface treatments was always marginal in the field of archaeometallurgy. Their popularity is still highly uncertain within most of the medieval material culture, sometimes their function is unclear as well. This case study showcases identified surface treatments - gilding, silvering and tinning – on several artefacts from the Middle Ages using X-ray fluorescence (XRF) spectrometry and optical microscope. The main questions of the topics are the following: what are the best analytical methods for identifying surface methods?; how popular were gilding, silvering and tinning in medieval times? The results of the research were very interesting and instructive. To begin with, on several artefacts the surface treatments could only be identified with the analytical methods, which also means that they were misinterpreted previously. The latter is more prominent in the case of 5 S-end lock rings, which were all originally interpreted as silver artefacts; using the analytical methods all of them could be identified as silvered bronze jewellery. This result shows that researches like this are not only important from an archaeometallurgical perspective, but also very useful for classical archaeology too. My study not only acknowledges these problems, but also offers a practical method for future researches into different surface treatments.

The Datability of Nuremberger Yellow Brass

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Keywords: XRF, Candlesticks, Late Medieval, Early Modern, Yellow brass, Dating

The topic of my presentation is my current research, which involves the application of X-ray fluorescence (XRF) analysis to medieval brass candlesticks from Nuremberg. I wrote my bachelor's thesis on this topic and will continue this research during my master's studies at Eötvös Loránd University in Budapest. I collected nearly 40 fragments of candlesticks and chandeliers from three museums from one of the largest counties in Hungary, Bács-Kiskun county. From these, I selected seven pieces for XRF analysis, which I conducted at the HUN-REN Institute for Nuclear Research with the help of Dr. Furu Enikő. To help date these objects, I relied on the work of Josef Riederer, who developed a database and a method for identifying the approximate age of any Nuremberger yellow brass objects. He examined late medieval and early modern grave plates made from this alloy in a graveyard in Nuremberg and realized that a specific composition of yellow brass was used during particular time periods. Due to their excellent datability, he was able to connect specific compositions to distinct time periods. After hundreds of compositional analyses, Riederer was able to determine with certainty that any type of Nuremberger yellow brass cast objects can be dated to a few decades. The aim of my presentation is to demonstrate the use of Riederer's method on late medieval and early modern yellow candlesticks using XRF technology, while highlighting its potentials and limitations.

The TerraLID metadata profile: Uniformly describing lead isotope data in archaeology

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Keywords: Archaeometallurgy, Lead isotopes, Research data

Since its first application to archaeological artefacts almost 60 years ago, the analysis of lead isotopes evolved into the default method for reconstructing the raw material provenance of non-ferrous metals. Pre-requisite is a collection of data with known raw material provenance to compare the artefact data to. Unfortunately, the compilation and re-use of this data is often hampered, among others, by the large variety and different levels of detail of their metadata. TerraLID aims to improve this situation by providing a digital research data infrastructure with a single point of access for the publication, storage, and access of lead isotope data combined with a web application for working with such data and submitting them. An essential part of this research data infrastructure is a metadata profile for the uniform description of the data and their metadata. Development of this metadata profile aims towards its universal applicability, easy extensibility and efficient storage of information. Guided by the input of the TerraLID editors as community representatives, the entire community is currently encouraged to comment on its draft. As part of this community feedback process, this contribution will present the overall structure and takes a closer look on some aspects to spark discussion and encourage feedback from the audience.

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Strontium Isotopic and Proteomic Analyses on the Human Remains of the KGK VI sites of Sultana and Gumelnița, Romania

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Keywords: Strontium, Amelogenin, Chalcolithic, Romania

This talk will explore the results of the strontium isotopic analyses on the tooth enamel of the human remains found in the Eneolithic graves excavated at the Sultana-Malu Roșu and Gumelnița necropolises (Romania) and on modern plants of the area used to create a baseline. It will also present the results of the proteomic analysis of amelogenin of human tooth enamel that we also performed to obtain reliable sex estimations, on individuals whose remains were the least preserved. Finally, it will discuss the potential role of individual mobility and marital alliances as a driving force behind the emergence of the Kodjadermen-Gumelnița-Karonovo VI (KGK VI) material culture in the eastern Balkans during the 5th millennium BC.

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Early Thoughts on Childhood in Early Medieval Iceland (10th–13th Centuries AD)

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Keywords: Biological anthropology, Medieval Iceland, Childhood

While the study of childhood in the past has gained considerable momentum in recent decades, both from social archaeological and bioanthropological perspectives, it remains largely unexplored within Icelandic biological anthropology. To date, I am the only researcher actively investigating this field. In response to this gap, I conducted the first bioarchaeological study of early life courses at four sites in Northern Iceland dating from the 10th to 13th centuries AD. The results revealed significant growth disruption in infants and high mortality rates between 1.5 and 4.5 postnatal months. These patterns point to poor maternal and infant health and a postnatal decline in immunological and nutritional support, likely shaped by the adverse living conditions that characterized early medieval Northern Iceland. These included a harsh and unstable climate, nutritional deficiencies, poor indoor air quality, and high exposure to infectious diseases within domestic spaces. Building on these findings, my PhD project will further examine childhood health, mortality, and social identity at these four sites. It will incorporate methods such as dimorphic peptide analysis of dental enamel for biological sex estimation in non-adults and stable isotope analysis to reconstruct breastfeeding and weaning practices. In my presentation, I would like to outline the results of my preliminary research alongside the principal aims and hypotheses of my ongoing doctoral project.

Gender, Age, and Social Identity in the Middle Bronze Age Burials from Western Hungary

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Keywords: Funerary practices, Sex-specific peptide, Gender intensity, Stable isotopes, Diet, Radiocarbon dating, Bronze Age

This study examines the social structure of communities that inhabited the area of present-day Western Hungary between 2200/2100 and 1600/1500 BC, using archaeometric methods for sex determination, radiocarbon dating, and dietary reconstruction based on excavated burials. During this period, the region functioned as a cultural borderland between the inhumation funerary traditions of the Central European Únětice culture and the cremation rites practiced by groups of the Carpathian Basin, such as the Kisapostag and Transdanubian Encrusted Pottery cultures. Within this context, our research focuses on the previously underexplored Gáta-Wieselburg communities, which are notable for their inhumation burial practices. In addition to archaeological and anthropological analysis at Hungarian sites associated with this culture, we conducted stable isotope and geochemical studies at two cemeteries in Nagycenk (61 burials in total), both distinguished by their rich assemblages of status-related grave goods. By integrating observations for funerary practices, anthropological data, and peptide-based sex identification, our study aims to explore the emergence and extent of gender and age-based social differentiation within these communities. A further key question is whether the grave goods and isotopic evidence for diet reflect patterns of emerging permanent social stratification in the Middle Bronze Age.

The Whole, the Missing and the Disturbed: Exploring Post-Burial Practices in the Langobard Cemetery of Gyirmót-Homokdomb

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Keywords: Langobards, Grave reopening, Archaeoethanatology, Bioarchaeology, Migration Period, Post-burial practice, Mortuary archaeology

Grave reopenings in the 6th-century Langobard-period cemetery of Gyirmót–Homokdomb, located in Northern Transdanubia, offer a valuable opportunity to explore post-burial interactions with the dead during the Migration Period. This study applies archaeoethanological and bioarchaeological approaches and methods to examine selected burials showing evidence of disturbance. The analysis focuses on the stratigraphic and spatial characteristics of selected/ these reopened graves, including alterations in skeletal positions, and the possible removal of bones and grave goods. Particular attention is given to identifying patterns of disturbance and assessing their consistency across multiple features. Preliminary bioanthropological observations aim to detect indicators of post-depositional manipulation, such as the rearrangement of skeletal elements or damage not attributable to natural taphonomic processes. Material culture associated with disturbed contexts is also examined for evidence of fragmentation, redeposition, or spatial reorganization. Rather than assuming a single motivation behind these reopenings, this study explores a range of possible explanations—ritual, social, or practical—within the broader framework of Langobard mortuary customs. The ongoing analysis seeks to refine our understanding of the role of reopened graves in the funerary landscape and the significance of post-burial practices during this transitional period.

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Experimental Research of Medieval Bone Skates

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Keywords: Use-wear analysis, Experimental archaeology, Bone skates

Since the 19th century, bone tools made from the long bones of large ungulates have been the subject of interest in both Hungarian and international research. Contrary to earlier interpretations some of the finds in the Carpathian Basin may have actually been bone fishing net weights in the Middle Ages, but a large number of objects identified as bone skates have also been found. In order to shed light on the function of the medieval and early modern bones, I carried out use-wear analysis, which are closely related to experimental archaeology. To determine the function of the objects and understand their use, I also included ethnographic parallels in the study. During the experiment, I was able to perform the method of skating known from medieval descriptions and compare the use-wear traces on the bones with those observed on the archaeological objects, thus proving that some of the finds were indeed used for skating on ice.

Archaeozoological Investigations in the Late Neolithic Site of Moftinu Mare-Hamiliz (Northwest Romania)

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Keywords: Archaeozoology, Late Neolithic, Settlement, Animal bones

The archaeological site at Moftinu Mare-Hamiliz is located in northwestern Romania, on the terrace formed by the flow of the Murai stream into the Ecedea marsh. The site was identified in 2016 during field investigations for the installation of a gas pipeline and a gas collection and purification station. Archaeological excavations carried out in the same year identified a settlement and a necropolis dating back to the Late Neolithic period, the Herpály culture. Research at the settlement continued in 2021. The Neolithic settlement at Moftinu Mare is remarkable for its rich ceramic material, lithic materials and animal bones. The archaeozoological material studied comes from the settlement, and was excavated during the campaigns of 2016 and 2021. Primary archaeozoological analysis showed a predominance of domestic species, especially cattle (*Bos taurus*). Other animals identified in the settlement are domestic pigs (*Sus domesticus*), sheep/goats (*Ovis/Capra*) and canids (*Canis familiaris*). Hunting represented a less important occupation of the Moftinu Mare community; among the wild animals present at the site we find red deer (*Cervus elaphus*), roe deer (*Capreolus capreolus*), aurochs (*Bos primigenius*) and bison (*Bison bison*). Archaeozoological investigations have identified several traces of disarticulation (cut marks) and gnawing on the distal epiphyses of cattle bones. The processing of deer and roe deer antlers was also attested in the settlement. Bone pathology was observed on one of the bovine metacarpals.

Ancient Parasitic Infection: A Millennium-Old Probable Echinococcal Cyst Discovered in an Avar Period Burial

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Keywords: Parasitology, Cyst, Paleopathology, Bioarchaeology

During the excavation of a late Avar-period cemetery in Gyomaendrőd, Hungary in February 2023, the archaeologists of the Munkácsy Mihály Museum (MMM) observed an unusual feature in grave S113, located between the lower right ribs. They identified a relatively large, calcinated anomaly. A remnant of a cyst caused by a parasite infection likely developed in the liver was successfully recovered. This discovery is important because such archaeological cysts are known from fewer than ten publications worldwide. *Echinococcus granulosus* is a tapeworm that causes cystic echinococcosis, also known as hydatid disease. Humans are intermediate hosts, becoming infected by ingesting eggs from contaminated dog feces. In the human host, the parasite larvae migrate to different organs, mostly liver. It grows, creating hydatid cysts that can reach 2-3 cm in diameter annually. The carrier may remain unaware of the infection for years. In the case of the cyst found in Gyomaendrőd, we are particularly fortunate because multiple institutions have joined the research. Collaborators include colleagues from the MMM and the HNM, as well as researchers from HUN-REN, the National Center for Public Health and Pharmacy, and Semmelweis University. In addition to SEM, Raman spectroscopy, and micro XRF analyses, we also conducted genetic and micro-CT examinations. Our goal is to thoroughly investigate the cyst, which will not only expand our knowledge about this disease but also allow us to infer information about the hygienic and health conditions of the population from that period.

Pottery Technology and Neolithization in the Middle Tagus Basin: Preliminary Petrographic Insights

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Keywords: Neolithic, Pottery, Technology, Characterization, Petrography

In the early 20th century, Neolithic studies in central Iberia were strongly influenced by Bosch Gimpera's theory of Cultural Circles, which classified the region within the so-called Cave Culture. By the late 20th century, however, new archaeological discoveries and the introduction of radiocarbon dating prompted a significant reassessment of this framework. The Middle Tagus Basin emerged as a key area for understanding these shifts. This paper re-evaluates the role of the Middle Tagus Basin, strategically located between the Atlantic and Mediterranean spheres, in the broader Neolithization process of the Iberian Peninsula. It presents preliminary petrographic data on pottery production from this region, based on both petrographic thin-section analysis and macroscopic examination of ceramic assemblages from Neolithic sites. Additionally, it offers a comprehensive review of all published radiocarbon dates for this period in the area, recalibrated using the IntCal20 curve. The study explores the correlation between chronological data, archaeological contexts, and ceramic technological traits, aiming to define the distinctive features of Neolithic pottery in the Middle Tagus and to reassess their role in the spread of Neolithic traditions across the peninsula. Ultimately, this research raises a broader question: to what extent can the Iberian Plateau be considered a peripheral territory, dependent on other Neolithic centers such as the Levant or southern Iberia?

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Understanding Copper Age Pottery Function Through Morphometric and Organic Residue Analysis

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Keywords: Organic residue analysis, Pottery function, Copper Age

Understanding the function of Copper Age pottery requires a complex approach, beginning with the study of size and form, which can determine the range of possible uses of pots. When complemented by organic residue analysis, which provides crucial information about the past contents of individual pots, these possibilities can be narrowed down. Combined with morphometric analysis, this allows for inferences about food processing methods to be made. The type and frequency of certain commodities can also indicate a broader picture of the economy and subsistence strategies. In Transdanubia and the Budapest area, daily life within settlements remains a relatively unknown aspect of Copper Age communities. This includes the function(s) of known pottery forms, culinary practices and the importance of livestock husbandry, especially regarding the use of secondary animal products. To gain insight into these topics, the results of morphometric and organic residue analyses from Early and Middle Copper Age (4500-3800/3700 BCE) settlements in the Budapest area are presented. Based on the results, there was no clear correlation between the form and the type of content. It was confirmed that pottery was mainly used for processing ruminant and non-ruminant products in the Early Copper Age, and dairy processing became common only at the end of the Middle Copper Age.

The Traces of the Potter's Hand: Pottery Experimental Reference Collection for the Analysis of Copper Age Vessels from the Carpathian Basin

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Keywords: Pottery technology, Experimental archaeology, Multiscalar analysis, Laser scanning confocal microscopy, Copper Age

One of the most important issues of the technological analysis of pottery forming and surface treatment is to establish a relationship between the observed traces of forming and surface treatment and the characteristics of the pottery making (e.g. techniques, tools, drying levels) that resulted in these kinds of traces. To define this connection, ethnographical or experimental references are essential, allowing us to observe both the process of pottery making and the traces of the created vessel. Several pottery forming and surface treatment techniques can be identified in the Early and Middle Copper Age in the Carpathian Basin (4500/4450–3800/3700 calBC). Some of these are widely known from experimental and ethnographical studies (e.g. modelling). However, other techniques have little or no parallel in other contexts (e.g. reverse coiling technique) and even the well-known techniques are often problematic. Although numerous works discuss these well-known techniques, not everyone understands the same thing under the same expression (e.g. burnishing or polishing). Therefore, we created an experimental reference collection that focuses on these lesser-known or problematic forming and surface treatment techniques. This was followed by the comparison of the experimental and archaeological vessels. For this, we used a multiscalar analytical approach, including the macro- and microscopic examination of the samples. The latter was carried out with laser scanning confocal microscopy to obtain quantitative data from the surface, besides the qualitative observations. As a result, we gained an in-depth understanding of the Copper Age pottery-making processes.

Technological Investigation of the Middle Bronze Age Late Hatvan and Füzesabony Style Pottery from the Borsod Plain Region, Northeastern Hungary

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Keywords: Bronze Age, Carpathian Basin, Ceramic technology, Raw materials, Firing technology

During the Middle Bronze Age (2000/1900–1600/1500 BC), different “tell-building” communities can be distinguished in Central and Eastern Hungary, such as the Vátya, Hatvan, Füzesabony and Maros groups. These groups were separated on the basis of different pottery style and burial rite, but their common characteristic is that they lived in tell settlements. This lifestyle required long-term habitation, so the settlements were usually occupied for several hundred years, sometimes by people of different culture groups. In Northeastern Hungary at the Borsod plain region, the Late Hatvan and the Füzesabony groups appeared in this period. These groups can be distinguished by distinct burial rite and pottery style, although their vessels can often be found in the same settlement or cemetery. Within their ceramic assemblages they used different, characteristic vessel shapes and decorations. Therefore, three Middle Bronze Age sites were analysed in this research, Bogács-Paszagpuszta a Late Hatvan/Füzesabony tell-like settlement, its eastern neighbour Novaj-Földvár, a Füzesabony tell settlement and Vatta-Telek-oldal-dűlő a Füzesabony/Late Hatvan cemetery. Our aim was to detect and compare the raw materials, tempers and firing techniques of Late Hatvan and Füzesabony style ceramics, using thin section petrography, x-ray powder diffraction and scanning electron microscopy with energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy. The goal of this research was to detect technological differences or similarities within the two distinct pottery styles, and the raw material analysis of a specific Late Hatvan type fine ware.

Comparing Archaic Corinthian Pottery Through SEM-EDS and Optical Microscopy: A case study

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Keywords: Corinthian pottery, Optical microscopy, SEM-EDS, Chemical analysis, Tenea, Corinth, Mageri site

Ancient Tenea was a significant city in the eastern vicinity of ancient Corinth, which flourished throughout antiquity. Since 2013, remnants of the ancient city have been excavated in the context of the systematic archaeological research, which is conducted between the area of modern Chiliomodi - Klenia. During the excavation of the city, a significant amount of archaic pottery was collected, both in residential areas and in its cemeteries. Some of the ceramic vessels have no similar shape in the international literature. This led the excavators to the assumption of the existence of local pottery production. To confirm this assumption, pottery sherds from three different sites were examined through archaeometric means. These came from an archaic deposit in ancient Tenea, an archaic cemetery near Ancient Corinth, and an archaic deposit at Mageri site. The present study examines whether Tenea's archaic samples present similarities or differences in comparison to the archaic pottery of Mageri site and ancient Corinth. Examination of the ceramics was conducted through optical analysis and SEM-EDS in the laboratory of the Faculty of Sciences of the Aristotle University in Thessaloniki. The study of ceramics showed that the samples from all the excavations were very fine-grained and calcareous. Differences can be detected considering the color of the fabric and the firing properties. These elements could indicate a different clay origin or different techniques used in this pottery production or even different workshops.

Unchanging Tastes: Material Choices in Hellenistic and Roman Storage Vessels from Nea Paphos

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Keywords: Ceramics, Petrography, Storage vessels, Pithoi, Dolium, Hellenistic, Roman, Nea Paphos, Cyprus

This presentation discusses the differences in technological choices made by potters during the Hellenistic and Roman periods at the archaeological site of Nea Paphos in Cyprus, with a particular focus on storage vessels: Greek pithoi and Roman dolia. The study aims to define which features of these vessels resulted from intentional technological decisions and which were influenced by local conditions, such as raw material availability or workshop organization. The research is based on 30 ceramic fragments from both public and private spaces, dated between the 4th century BCE and the 7th century CE, excavated by the Polish Archaeological Mission at Maloutena and Agora. The samples were subjected to petrographic analysis and compared with other ceramic categories from the site, as well as from selected Cypriot sites exhibiting similar economic transformations. Contrary to expectations of diverse clay usage, the research reveals a strong tendency among potters to rely on a single clay source, even when alternatives were available. However, variability was noted in the selection of tempering material used to modify the properties of the raw material. The evidence suggests a higher degree of specialization during the Roman period, and, alongside increased external influence on production techniques. Rather than constructing rigid typologies, this presentation seeks to explore ancient society through its material culture. By examining storage vessels, it aims to uncover cultural patterns and technological practices not easily accessible through other types of archaeological evidence. The findings highlight how these vessels reflect broader socio-economic and technological transformations in the ancient Mediterranean world.

Geochemical and Mineralogical Provenance analysis of West African Pottery

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Keywords: Pottery, Provenance analysis, pXRF, Mineralogy

In historical periods, trade networks in West Africa are documented through written sources and exotic artifacts. However, both are rare and represent only a limited portion of past exchange activities. The provenance analysis of ceramics, as a common find category, can offer new insights into the movement of artifacts. Our approach follows a two-step process. First, sherds that were likely produced locally were selected from archaeological sites across various regions of West Africa. This selection was based on attributes such as shape, decoration, and petrofabric. These sherds were then subjected to geochemical analysis to determine the regional chemical composition of the ceramics. For this purpose, we used portable X-ray fluorescence (pXRF), which enables the rapid analysis of a large number of samples. In doing so, we were able to establish geochemically distinct reference groups for many regions of West Africa. In the second step, sherds identified as non-local based on their attributes were analyzed to verify their non-local origin. Using the reference groups, it is also possible to assign these vessels to potential source regions, thus tracing interregional connections in medieval West Africa. While pXRF is well-suited for mass sampling, it also has certain limitations. Therefore, selected sherds are subjected to more precise geochemical and mineralogical analyses. These complementary methods provide a more detailed understanding of the clays used in pottery production. The combination of rapid and precise geochemical and mineralogical approaches enables the efficient analysis of a large number of samples, while producing robust results.

Exploring AI-assisted Image Segmentation for Ceramic Thin Section Analysis: Some Experience with TagLab

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Keywords: Artificial intelligence, Ceramic petrography, Segmentation, Automated images, Archaeometry

Ceramic petrography plays a fundamental role in archaeometric studies, offering insights into raw materials choice, manufacturing techniques, and provenance. However, the method is time-consuming and relies heavily on expert interpretation. In this context, emerging AI-based tools offer promising opportunities to enhance the efficiency, reproducibility, and scalability of thin-section analysis. This study presents an experimental application of TagLab, an open-source software originally developed for the analysis of large-scale orthomosaics of marine corals, to the analysis of microphotographs of ceramic thin sections. The aim is to explore how TagLab's AI-assisted segmentation features, particularly its trainable classifiers, can be adapted to automatically recognise and annotate petrographic components such as inclusions, pores, and matrix areas in different ceramic fabrics. The application of this tool to new scenarios showed several challenges, especially due to differences in scale, resolution, and the use of polarised light in microscopy. Nevertheless, with appropriate image pre-processing and calibration, TagLab proved capable of supporting semi-automated annotation and providing both visual and quantitative data outputs. The approach offers potential benefits in terms of speed, repeatability, and partial reduction of interpretative subjectivity. While still in progress, this work highlights the potential of AI-driven tools in ceramic petrography and encourages their integration in archaeometric workflows.

Iberian Majolica Finds in the Medieval Kingdom of Hungary?

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Keywords: Lustre, Cobalt blue decoration, SEM-EDS, mXRF

Two blue and white glazed ceramic fragments featuring leaf motifs and lustre decoration were recovered during archaeological excavations in Budapest and Győr (Hungary). Comparative research into published majolica finds from the territory of the medieval Kingdom of Hungary revealed a vessel in the collection of the Museum of Applied Arts bearing identical decorative patterns. Based on typological and stylistic analysis, the fragments were dated to the first half of the 15th century and attributed to the renowned majolica workshops of Manises and Paterna (Valencia, Spain). In the last decades, several studies have addressed the archaeometric characterization of raw materials and production technologies employed in these workshops. The results indicate that the ceramic bodies and glaze pigments were made from different raw materials in the different periods of these long-lived workshops. Our aim was to determine if the Hungarian finds were indeed made in these workshops or in another, which imitated their decorative style. Due to the uniqueness of these fragments, destructive analysis was limited to a single sample, while the others were examined using only non-invasive techniques (SEM-EDS and mXRF). Preliminary results indicate that the ceramic bodies were produced using calcareous raw materials, consistent with those used in Valencian manufacture. However, notable differences were observed in the glaze compositions. The laboratory analyses were funded by the Ministry of Innovation and Technology (TKP 2021-NKTA-15).

Prehistoric Sites in Turkmenistan: A GIS-Based Overview of Spatial and Temporal Patterns

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Keywords: Turkmenistan, Prehistory, GIS mapping, Spatial analysis, Jeitun culture, Chalcolithic

Turkmenistan, a Central Asian country, remains a relatively understudied region in terms of archaeological research. This study aims to provide an overview of all prehistoric archaeological sites discovered in the region, from the first excavations in the early 20th century to 2023. A comprehensive literature review was conducted to compile an inventory of prehistoric sites and approximate their geographic coordinates. Geographic Information Systems (GIS) were further exploited to elaborate spatial distribution maps and analyze site patterns across time periods. A total of 103 sites were recorded, with more than half belonging to the Neolithic, Chalcolithic, and Bronze Age settlements in the southern region of the country. Another significant cluster of Bronze Age and Iron Age sites was recorded in the Murgap alluvial fan area in southeast Turkmenistan, indicating that these two regions have received the most extensive archaeological attention. The oldest known sites, dating back to the late Upper Paleolithic period, are located in the western Balkan region. While the western region has been studied to some extent, the northern region remains largely underexplored. The resulting maps and period-based classifications offer a foundational resource for future archaeological research and emphasize the need for more systematic investigation across less-studied regions of Turkmenistan.

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Geophysical Research of Rural Settlements of the Roman Period in the Surroundings of Crumerum (Nyergesújfalu, Hungary)

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Keywords: Geophysics, Non-invasive archaeology, Rural settlement system, Roman period, Pannonia

The research of the rural settlement system in the Roman period has become an important topic in Hungarian archaeology in recent decades, as has the topographical work with a holistic approach. My research takes place in Komárom-Esztergom County, a few kilometres from the Danube, therefore the Roman ripa Pannonica and the quondam auxiliary fort of Crumerum. To understand the rural settlement system in the 1st–4th centuries, I focus on conducting non-invasive, mainly geophysical surveys at two sites (Lábatlan–Rábl valley and Nyergesújfalu–Gunyhóalji fields) using GPR and magnetometer. At both locations there are several buildings with stone foundations, which is not atypical for Pannonian vici, but certainly shows a higher level of development. I complement the geophysical component with field surveys and examination of the archaeological finds from the surface. I compare the results of the sites to each other as well as to the wider Pannonian context of the buildings and other objects found during the surveys. In the long term, I would like to extend the research with more sites to a micro-regional level in order to gain a deeper understanding of this area in the Roman period.

Application of Non-Destructive Field Investigation Methods in the Archaeological Study of a Medieval Ruined Settlement in Tolna County, Hungary

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Keywords: Non-destructive, Geophysics, GIS, Aerial, Medieval

As part of my BA thesis in Archaeology, I conducted a non-destructive investigation of a deserted medieval settlement in Tolna County, Hungary. The research employed a combination of methods, including historical map analysis, archival and archaeological aerial photography, magnetometer surveying, and 3D photogrammetric survey using a drone. My primary tasks included executing some of the surveys, processing and evaluating the archaeological data, and interpreting the results. I also reconstructed the site's topography using archival cartographic, geological, and geographic sources. The integration of multiple survey techniques allowed for the identification of numerous structural features of the former settlement. Different methods revealed different aspects of the archaeological record, and their combined interpretation provided a more comprehensive picture of the site. All data were processed and analyzed within a geoinformatics (GIS) software environment, which also facilitated the reconstruction of the landscape and the settlement layout. The results revealed the main street, property boundaries, ditches, a gate, and the location of the medieval church complex in Gyánt. In this area, two distinct church structures were identified, although their spatial and chronological relationship remains uncertain. In the riverside zone, the remains of a workshop and several mills were inferred. These were supported by environmental reconstruction, written sources, and the earlier discovery of millstone fragments, indicating their proximity to the river. This research highlights the effectiveness of integrating non-destructive methods and GIS analysis in the archaeological study of deserted medieval settlements.

Characterization and Analysis of Wall Painting Fragments from the Sandrigo Estate of Aquileia for the Determination of a Chronological Framework

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Keywords: Petrography, Wall paintings, Aquileia, Mortar, Chronology

This study investigates the raw material and production techniques employed in the Roman wall-painting fragments collected from the Sandrigo Estate, east of the River Port of Aquileia. 10 representative samples were chosen for analysis from nuclei collected from secondary debris. Transmitted- Light Polarized Optical Microscopy (TL-OM) on thin sections was adopted for petrographic analysis of preparation mortars. Such analysis has unfolded a progressive evolution in the choice of raw materials employed in the preparation of the wall-paintings. In fact, stylistic and petrographic research on wall fragments from Aquileia conducted in past years aided in the determination of a chronological framework ranging from the 2nd c. BCE to the 4th c. CE (Dilaria et al. 2021). By comparing the results of the analyses of the Sandrigo samples with this reference “baseline” it is therefore possible to reconstruct their probable chronology. The main characterizing element relies on the preparation of the uppermost intonachino layer. Most of the samples were made adopting methods typical of the Republican/Early Imperial periods, characterized by distinct layers of tectorium and an intonachino composed almost entirely of sparry calcite. On the other hand, other samples appear to follow preparation practices of the Late Antique period, where intonachino was made with common fluvial sand. Moreover, via Raman Spectroscopy pigments have been characterized. These include the common Roman palette (hematite, carbon black, goethite), but interestingly the best executed samples were also the ones where more expensive pigments were detected such as cinnabar, sometimes mixed with Egyptian blue.

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Urns under the Microscope: Petrographic Analysis of Eight Iron Age Pots from Funen, Denmark

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Keywords: Petrography, Geochemistry, Ceramics

This project is a small petrographic case study of eight ceramic pots used as urns at a burial site in Bellinge Fælled near Odense in Denmark dated to around 300-500 AD (Younger Danish Iron Age). Four pots with ornamentations and four without were chosen to investigate any mineralogical and technological differences between the two groups of ceramics in order to examine whether they could have been produced by different potters in different local areas. The petrographic analysis of the eight pots has shown that there is a difference between the urns with and without ornamentations. The pottery with ornamentations has been carefully produced from similar clay- and temper sources with uniform technology which reflects a specific recipe and technology for this type of pottery. The four studied pots without ornamentations, on the other hand, show variations in the clay- and temper sources and in the production process. These pots could have been produced by different individuals and might have been reused from the household pottery. The eight pots have additionally been analysed with the geochemical analysis ICP-MA/ES to investigate their provenance. This has shown that the ceramics were all produced locally on the island of Funen but with clay from four different clay sources. Based on this, the pottery must have been produced by different potters with extensive knowledge of the materials and resources, who were able to select and use different resources for different types of pots with different purposes.

Archaeometric Analyses of Pozzolanitic Mortars in Roman Thermal and Hydraulic Constructions at Nora, Sardinia

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Keywords: Historic mortars, Pozzolanitic mortars, Provenance studies

This research presents the preliminary results of the compositional characterization of the structural and lining mortars of two relevant Roman Middle Imperial period buildings in the ancient city of Nora (Sardinia, Italy). Specifically, the objects of the analysis are the thermal complex of 'Terme a Mare' and the aqueduct, both built around the 2nd-3rd century AD. Most of the analysed samples are hydraulic mortars enriched with different types of pozzolanitic aggregates that are primarily constituted by pyroclastic material such as pumices/tuffs, obsidians, or ceramic fragments. Mortar samples and pyroclastic aggregates were analysed adopting a multi-analytical protocol. Mortars were analysed, coupling Transmitted-Light Polarized Optical Microscopy (TL-OM) and Scanning Electron Microscopy with Energy Dispersive X-Ray Analysis (SEM-EDS), providing a detailed characterization of their compositions and production techniques. Moreover, SEM-EDS together with XRF (X-Ray Fluorescence) were adopted to analyse the pozzolanitic volcanic aggregates and to define their provenance based on the comparison with geochemical reference literature. The preliminary archaeometric analysis allowed us to investigate the petro-mineralogical compositions of each mortar sample, leading to the identification of four distinct mortar groups: aerial lime mortars, pumice/tuff-enriched lime mortars and cocchiopesto enriched with obsidians were mainly employed for structural purposes, whereas cocchiopesto enriched with pumice/tuff was primarily used for lining of hydraulic infrastructures. Through the geochemical analysis it was possible to establish that pumices and tuffs were imported from the Phlegraean volcanic district (Naples), while obsidian most presumably came from the Monte Arci outcrop (southwestern Sardinia).

Textile Remains of the Early Avar period Cemetery at Babarc

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Keywords: Archaeological textiles, Textile production

During the excavations carried out between 2021 and 2023 in the surroundings of Babarc in Southwest Transdanubia (Hungary), the Janus Pannonius Museum and the Ásatárs Ltd. uncovered an exceptionally rich Early Avar period cemetery. The parallels of the archaeological material reveal in many cases connections with the Byzantine and Merovingian worlds, while the parallels of more conservative burial practices are mainly known from the Eastern part of Hungary (Transtisza region), where a community from the Eastern European Steppe settled during the period. According to our present knowledge, textile remains related to 24 objects/groups of objects have been recognized from 13 graves in the cemetery, mostly related to elements of the garment. Most of the textiles are woven from z-twist yarns in compact or loose tabby with regular yarn thickness. But tabby woven textiles with various yarn thickness also occur in more graves (SNR 4, SNR 11, SNR 25, SNR 26). In the case of a male grave (SNR 2023/1), the woven pattern or embroidery is also clearly identifiable on the textile remains. In two graves (SNR 73, SNR 94) the corrosion of the iron belt fittings has preserved at least two layers of fabric remains, suggesting that the deceased men were buried in multi-layered or lined clothing.

Archaeometric Analysis of Late Sarmatian Pottery Recovered from Tázlár- Templomhegy Settlement

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Keywords: Ceramic petrography, Provenance analysis

The Late Sarmatian settlement of Tázlár–Templomhegy is located in the central part of the Homokhátság region in the Duna–Tisza Interfluve, Hungary. Its pottery assemblage includes all known pottery types of the period. Despite this, no suitable clay sources or evidence of local pottery production (e.g. workshops) have been identified in the vicinity. The aim of our research is to determine the potential origin of these vessels and to narrow down the source areas of the tempers used. In addition to petrographic analysis, we applied several analytical techniques including Raman microscopy, SEM-EDS, cathodoluminescence (CL) microscopy and spectroscopy, and X-ray powder diffraction (XRD). Petrographic results allowed us to define five petrographic groups (T1–T5). For several of these, a likely origin in known pottery workshops could be proposed, including those at Sándorfalva–Eperjes, Nagymágocs–Paptanya, and Üllő pottery workshops. XRD data provided estimates of the firing temperatures for each group. We also attempted to identify the source region of the granitoid tempering found in Group T5 attributed to the Nagymágocs–Paptanya workshop. This was done through comparative analysis with granitoid rock samples using CL spectroscopy. The results indicate that the closest match – based on textural, mineralogical, and CL spectral characteristics of feldspars – points to the Codru granitoids of the Apuseni Mountains, Romania. These findings contribute to our understanding of regional pottery production and distribution networks during the Late Sarmatian period.

Clay and Pots from Eneolithic period

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Keywords: Petrography

The Gumelnitsa culture is one of the most representative expressions of the Eneolithic in the northern Balkan Peninsula, with a range covering vast regions of southern Romania - Muntenia, eastern Oltenia, southeastern Moldavia and Dobrogea - as well as the southern Danubian territories of Bulgarian and Greek Thrace. This extension defines the Gumelnitsa-Kodžadermen-Karanovo VI cultural complex, whose communities evolved between 4600-3900 BC. Among the numerous archaeological sites identified, the tell of Popina-Bordușani (Ialomița county) is characterized by a complex stratigraphy, which reveals a succession of dwellings: from the Getic and Sarmatic to the Neolithic occupation, the latter being the most important and reaching, in places, a thickness of up to 8 meters. On the basis of chronological and cultural analysis, the tell is attributed to the A2 phase of the Gumelnitsa culture, reflecting a period of its maximum development. Among the essential aspects of daily life at that time was the production of pottery, a complex process involving careful selection of raw materials, shaping, decoration and firing in specialized kilns. The petrographic analyses carried out on the pottery from the tell of Popina-Bordușani have provided essential information on manufacturing technologies, the source of raw materials, but also the dynamics of craft traditions. The results of this research indicate the persistence of traditional customs and techniques in the process of making and using ceramic vessels, suggesting a cultural continuity deeply rooted within the local community.

First Archaeometric Results on Early Iron Age Ceramic Fragments from the Sanctuary of Apollo Pythios in Gortyn, Crete

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Keywords: Crete, Iron Age, Ceramic petrography, XRD, XRF, Gortyn

This poster presents the results of a multianalytical archaeometric analysis on ceramic material recovered from the sanctuary of Apollo Pythios in Gortyn, Crete (Greece), dated from the Protogeometric to the Archaic period. The analysis was performed on 46 ceramic sherds, consisting of a petrographic characterization through optical microscopy applied in 17 coarse grained samples, chemical analysis through X-ray fluorescence to identify the major, minor, and trace elements of 20 of the samples; and all the samples were characterized in terms of mineralogical composition through X-ray powder diffraction. The archaeometric data were statistically treated through cluster analysis and principal component analysis, and combined with the material's typo-chronological and macroscopic evaluation. The results reveal both continuity and transformation in paste preparation and fabric selection, hinting at a preference for typologically-driven ceramic recipes that seem to stay rather consistent throughout the archaeological periods. This work represents the first application of archaeometric methods in archaeological materials from Gortyn, offering valuable insights into local craft traditions and socio-cultural dynamics at a key site in Southern Crete. This study also contributes to broader discussions on material culture, ritual practices, and community formation during the formative centuries of the Cretan polis.

Tracing the Provenance of Roman Marble Statues Through Multi-Proxy Analysis

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Keywords: White marble, Provenance studies, Roman Thrace

A rigorous multi-proxy analytical approach determines the marble provenance of a life-size statue of Asclepius found in Dolni Pasarel, a site within the Roman province of Thrace, near ancient Serdica (present-day Sofia). The statue is sculpted from fine-grained white calcitic marble, prompting an investigation into its origin using archaeometric methodology. Stable isotope ratios ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$) were measured and plotted against a comprehensive reference dataset of over 5,700 samples from major ancient quarries. While the isotopic results alone showed significant overlap among sources such as Paros, Dokimeion, and Pentelicon, as well as local sources, a conclusive identification required enhanced resolution. To that end, trace element concentrations were determined using ICP-MS following selective dissolution with hot HNO_3 , thus targeting the carbonate matrix while excluding silicates. The data were subjected to multivariate statistical analysis (SPSS, STATISTICA), which successfully assigned the marble to the Pentelicon quarry in Attica (Greece). This methodological framework demonstrates the power of scientific archaeometry to address long-standing archaeological questions. The case underscores the importance of white marble provenance studies in reconstructing artistic production, trade mechanisms, and economic integration across the Roman Empire. By pinpointing the origin of this marble in Attica, the study illuminates the logistical reach and cultural priorities underpinning Roman supply chains in the provinces.

The Lord of the Shrooms: A Sensor's Quest to Detect Ancient Ergot

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Keywords: Psychoactive substances, Medieval, Fungi, Wood

The detection of ergot alkaloids in archaeological contexts opens new avenues for understanding the use of psychoactive or medicinal fungi in the past. Ergot, a parasitic fungus of cereal grains, produces alkaloids with psychoactive, vasoconstrictive, and hallucinogenic properties, which may have played roles in traditional medicine, ritual practices, or accidental poisonings. Inspired by recent archaeological findings from Vilnius Lower Castle, where ergot remnants were identified in wooden structures, this study presents a novel electrochemical sensor based on a riboflavin-derived molecularly imprinted polymer (MIP) for alkaloid detection. Ergot alkaloids, extracted from fresh *Claviceps purpurea* mushrooms collected in local fields, served as templates for MIP imprinting. Riboflavin (vitamin B2), a redox-active and naturally occurring molecule, was electropolymerized to form a conductive film capable of recognizing ergot compounds. Vitamins like riboflavin are promising building blocks for biocompatible sensors due to their inherent redox properties and environmental sustainability. The resulting sensor demonstrates promise for detecting trace compounds in archaeological residues, bridging analytical chemistry and cultural heritage research. This work highlights the potential of vitamin-derived polymers in developing biocompatible and archaeometrically relevant sensing tools.

Blue and Pink Across the Strait: Stylistic, Material, and Technical Study of 20th-Century Japanese and Taiwanese Ceramic Tableware

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Keywords: Japanese ceramics, Colonial Taiwanese ceramics, Underglaze blue, Pink glaze, Raman spectroscopy, XRF, Material culture

The material history of Taiwanese ceramics reflects a multi-layered colonial and political legacy. During Japanese colonial rule (1895–1945), Taiwan’s primary source of daily-use tableware gradually shifted from mainland Chinese to Japanese imports. By the 1940s, Japanese products dominated the local market. However, Japanese-established factories in Taiwan, such as the Taiwan Ceramic Co., Ltd. (台灣窯業株式會社) in Beitou, were also producing similar wares within the colony. Blue-and-white bowls with crane motifs (鶴紋碗) are commonly recovered in archaeological sites in both Japan and Taiwan. These bowls appear visually similar, making it difficult to determine their origin through stylistic analysis alone. Another recurring decorative scheme, featuring blue and pink glazes, suggests a shared visual repertoire that circulated between Japan and colonial Taiwan and continued into Taiwan’s postwar ceramic production. This study applies non-invasive Raman and XRF spectroscopy to investigate the representative ceramic sherds’ material and technical characteristics. Building on prior research showing that phase identification (Raman) and elemental composition (XRF) can reveal raw material sources and firing conditions, the analysis focuses on underglaze blue and pink colorants and trace impurities. The results reveal distinct regional patterns: gold-based pink glazes in Japanese ceramics, manganese-based pink in Taiwanese products, and variations in cobalt blue formulations, all contributing to regional identification. This comparative research advances understanding of the material culture of ceramic tableware in Japan and colonial Taiwan, tracing its development from raw materials and production techniques to decorative practices and the transregional circulation of glaze recipe knowledge in 20th-century East Asia.